

THE RULE OF LAW IN THE FOOD INDUSTRY

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Annotation: *Today, the issue of food is one of the most important issues on the agenda around the world. Climate change, a sharp increase in population and a corresponding increase in demand, is cited as the main reason for this. During this period, all states must provide their people with the necessary food.*

Keywords: *law enforcement, fisheries, fish species and morphology, profitability*

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, strategic work plans based on a clear account have been developed and laws and decisions have been adopted. The analysis was carried out on the ongoing reforms in the development of fisheries in the country in the most effective and promising areas of food security and the results achieved as a result of its implementation.

We know that fish products have a special place in the diet. Because fish products play a special role in meeting the needs of the population for protein and vitamins. In recent years, the analysis of large-scale political and economic work in this area in the country shows that in the last 5 years, 60,000 tons of fish products were grown, while this figure reached 400,000 tons.

Today, 84 species of fish such as Togay, Zogara, Laqqa, Amur, Akkoz, Turkestan Mustache, Amudarya and many other species have been returned to Uzbekistan. According to the Uzbek website gazeta.uz, more than 15 species of fish, including one of the oldest living creatures - the Amudarya Great Crested Bear and the Amudarya Gulf (Farel), are on the verge of extinction. Of the fish species present in Uzbekistan, 51 are carmonpsis and subspecies.

The country has taken a number of measures to ensure food security, including increasing the production of quality fish products, and the government pays great attention to the development of fisheries. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 29, 2020 No PP-4816 "On measures to support the fishing industry and increase its efficiency" provides ample opportunities for the rapid development of the fishing industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Today, white amur, white carp, rich in protein and meat, and rich in vitamins, is one of the main species grown in fisheries and is important for hunting. But there are also factors that seriously affect the development of the industry, among which parasitic diseases are the leading ones. Given the fact that parasitic diseases cause serious problems in the development of the fishing industry, a recommendation was developed entitled "Measures against helminthiasis and invasion of grass carp and whitefish."

The recommendations include the results of recent research conducted at the Institute of Botany and Zoology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan and are based on the literature. It contains scientifically based information on the description of helminthiasis of grass carp and whitefish living in the waters of the north-eastern part of Uzbekistan, the morphobiological characteristics of the pathogens, clinical signs, epizootology and prevention of the disease.

Information on the fish Amur (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) and Whitefish (*Gipofthalmis molitrix*) found in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. White amur (*Ctenopharyngodon idella*) is a fish belonging to the family of white amur-carp (Karpovye) and is the only representative of the genus *Ctenopharyngodon*. The body is elongated, tulip-shaped. The mouth is half lower. The rays on the shoulder girdle are the anal girdle. The number of vertebrae is 42-46. Occipital columns 13-16. The teeth of the larynx are two-rowed, pressed at the sides, and strongly incised. Length up to 1 meter, weight up to 32 kg. The natural range of the White Amur is the Amur Basin, the watershed of China. It is acclimatized in the watersheds of Central Asia and Kazakhstan.

It was brought to Uzbekistan from China in the 1960s. It is found in all plains of Uzbekistan. Currently, it is a fishing object in Uzbekistan, Russia, Ukraine, Kazakhstan, the United States and many European countries. Currently, despite the fact that it is widespread in the watersheds of the Amudarya, Syrdarya, Zarafshan and Kashkadarya, its number is small. In some parts of the Amudarya and Syrdarya there are cases of natural reproduction. In the Tallimarjan reservoir there are many white grasses, large in size, 67-87 cm long and weighing 6-10 kg. White amur is a fast-growing fish, weighing up to 45 kg in the Syrdarya basins.

White Amur lives a seasonal migration in water bodies. In summer it is mainly found in additional systems of water basins, in winter it crosses the riverbed and lives in deep places. Sexual matures in 5-6 years.

Urchishi-Amudarya and Syrdarya in April-May. Fertility is 1 billion. and spawns more than that.

The main food of the white amur is aquatic plants, which eat three species of small balikdar, worms, hash arot. Of the cultivated grasses, alfalfa, hashish peas, corn, concentrated fodder, silkworm moths, kunjara, and reed buds and the remaining parts of land plants in the water horse are favored.

Fisheries are artificially inseminated in ponds. It is used as a biomeliorator fish in the cleaning of water bodies (canals, ponds) from aquatic plants. In 1972, the Akkurgan fishery of Tashkent region achieved a fish yield of 65 ts / ha in polycultural conditions.

White-forehead fish (*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*). White or simple forehead. Freshwater herbivorous fish. Distinguished by rapid growth. When cared for in a pool, a one-year-old mother can grow up to 30 cm in length, weigh 700 g, two-year-olds 45 cm, 1,800 g, and three-year-olds 50 cm long and weigh 3,000 g. The mature fat mother is one meter long and weighs up to 8 kg. The body is silvery, the coins are small. The eye is located below the midline of the body. His mouth is pointing upwards. The edge of the abdomen is on the side of the abdomen, extending from the throat to the anal opening. The shoulder girdle has rays on the anal fins, the number of coins on the side line is 109-124. My throat teeth are single row. Body length 125 cm, weight up to 36 kg. The natural habitat of the white-tailed deer is the Amur Basin, China. It is acclimatized in the watersheds of Central Asia and Kazakhstan. It was brought to Uzbekistan in 1961 from China. Distributed in the middle reaches of the Syrdarya and Amudarya. In the Syrdarya and Amudarya rivers, when the water level rises or floods, the squirrel spawns. The white-tailed deer reaches sexual maturity at the age of 4-5 years and hatches in late April. Fertility is 3 million. and more around the calf. The calf is pelagic, floats in water and develops only in the current. Micro water was fed with algae (phyto plankton). Dongpeshona grows old. In the herd lake reservoir, the 1-2-year-old was 30.8-45.5 cm long and weighed 437-1449 grams, while the 3-year-old was 58 cm and 2860 grams. In the Amur River, there are also those whose forehead is 1 m long and weighs 16-20 kg. In the Tallimarjan reservoir there are also those weighing 10 kg and more. In

the Chimkurgan reservoir, those weighing 15-20 kg are being hunted selectively. The dung beetle feeds on phytoplankton, i.e. fine algae, and protects water bodies from flowering. The breeding of this fish in fisheries is yielding great economic benefits. Its fresh, salted and smoked products are delivered to our people in large quantities. Fish of hunting importance. It is mainly grown on fish farms.

Benefits of whitefish and amur fish in agriculture.

Now it is a great help in the operation of collectors in the field of agriculture. Natural collector-drains are necessary for canals. We know that the main reason for the large-scale swamping of soils in areas with ammunition is that the area is much larger than the total amount of precipitation. As a result, the following cases appear. 1. In areas with low water permeability and low slope, open water basins are formed. 2. Excessive soil moisture is mainly due to the premature rise of pressurized groundwater. 3. Wetting or excessive wetting of soils is due to both the rise of pressurized groundwater and the inflow of groundwater from adjacent areas in the above areas. This type of swamping can also occur in arid regions. In this case, the main cause of such swamping is amniotic irrigation water, which occurs mainly in areas where there is no natural permeability of groundwater. As a result, it is necessary to dig collector ditches.

Today, one of the biggest problems is the maintenance of collector-drainage networks. The bottom and slopes of the existing collector-drainage networks in Uzbekistan are overgrown with fire. As a result, their live cross-section decreases, the coefficient of roughness increases, the velocity of water flow decreases, the decontamination capacity of collectors and ditches decreases. In the early days of the new collector and ditches, they are especially overgrown. Open collector - The plants in the ditch network are cut and harvested. In the following years, white amur and dung forehead fish began to be bred in collectors and ditches. As a result, these fish began to multiply in collectors due to the fact that they multiplied very quickly and ate an amount of algae equal to their own weight per day. It naturally cleans the reservoir of fish and ensures a constant flow of groundwater. It is obvious that it reduces the technical cleaning of collectors per year and brings additional economic benefits.

Conclusion: As a result of timely and quality implementation of laws and decisions in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the demand for food in our country is being met. In nature, there are different types of fish. It is well known that fish is rich in healing and essential vitamins for humans. To date, along with the draft laws on the development of the fisheries sector, research is being conducted on the preservation and reproduction of endangered fish species and their transmission to future generations. For example, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 109 of March 9, 1992 "On the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan" banned the fishing of endangered species.

No matter how important the rate of profitability is in a market economy today, as a result of the implementation of these indicators on the basis of legal documents, the rate of increase in profit relative to costs will continue to rise. There is a decrease in the amount of expenditures. For example, on average, about 25-30 mln. If the sum is spent, this figure will increase every 2 or 3 years. Now, as a result of the establishment of fisheries in the collector canals, along with the annual income from fisheries, the need for cleaning of collector canals will be reduced.

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